

PEDAGOGICAL CLUSTER - A NEW INNOVATION ASPECT

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<https://www.doi.org/10.37547/ejmns-v03-i02-p1-38>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 12th February 2023

Accepted: 22th February 2023

Online: 23th February 2023

KEY WORDS

Cluster, innovation, pedagogy, method, methodology.

ABSTRACT

In this article the pedagogical educational cluster is a new innovative aspect.

Significant changes in society, of course, cover the sphere of education. Looking back at the work of the education system over the next quarter, we see a lot of positive work done in education and training in the years of independence. At the same time, it should be noted that there were some shortcomings in the provision of communication and communication between education types that ultimately led to a decline in the goal setting and the quality of education. The state policy on cadres has led to an imbalance in the distribution of staff in the regions as a result of incomplete socio-economic diversity of the regions, incompleteness of requirements and demands, in-depth study of demand and supply in the labor market. As a result, the need for pedagogical staff in some areas has not been met for many years. Over the next two years, a number of presidents and government resolutions have been passed on education and training in order to eliminate such deficiencies in the system. In particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Establishment of the Ministry of Pre-School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated September 30, 2017, "On Improvement of the Activity of the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated August 8, 2017, "On Improvement of the Activities of Secondary Specialized Vocational Educational Institutions" dated March 14, 2017 On Measures for Further Development of the Higher Education System "of April 20, 2017," On Measures for Further Improvement of Postgraduate Education System "dated May 22, 2017 the Presidential Decrees "on the improvement of the quality of cadres, in particular, the introduction of the experience of developed foreign countries. All of these documents, which are aimed at the development and improvement of the education system, have general aspects related to the introduction of innovations in the field, mastering foreign experience, supporting creative approaches, and strengthening the integration processes between education types. The problem of labor force shortage caused by inadequate cadre distribution in the education system has been the result of the lack of continuity, interdependence and lack of integration between the types of education directly envisioned by the continuous education system and the lack of prospective employee

prospects in the regions. In general, this problem is a comprehensive and multifaceted social issue and its solution can not be resolved by satisfying one or two reasons. This issue can be solved through the systematic work of regional khokimiyats and their respective subdivisions. In its turn, a new mechanism should be created in the system of pedagogical education, which should provide for mutual control of the types of education, both the competition and the benefits. The "Innovation Cluster for Pedagogical Education" model presented by the Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute in Tashkent region is regarded as a new innovative project that will eliminate the abovementioned deficiencies in the education system. This project is defined as the strategic direction of the institute, and today more than thirty professors and teachers are conducting scientific research to scientifically study this problem. Implementation of the model of "Innovation cluster of pedagogical education" in the process of elimination of divergence among educational forms of formation of continuous education, consolidation of them in common purpose, determination of continuity and continuity, formation of competition and control environment, creation of effective system of pedagogical activity theoretically based and productive solution. The "Innovation Cluster for Pedagogical Education" is a mimetic method, which implies the introduction of the cluster model, which is effective in the production sectors of the economy, in the educational process. In fact, the production chains have a number of raw materials, products and demand, and this sequence is also in the form of human capital as a pedagogical education system. This indicates that the introduction of an effective cluster model in the education system is theoretically justified. In general, due to the high social importance of pedagogical education in the sustainable development of society, modern requirements, problems in the system and the discrepancy between science and education roles in the resolution of these issues require the necessity of transferring continuing pedagogical education to the cluster development model. Implementation of the model of "Innovation cluster of pedagogical education" in the process of elimination of divergence among educational forms of formation of continuous education, consolidation of them in common purpose, determination of continuity and continuity, formation of competition and control environment, creation of effective system of pedagogical activity theoretically based and productive solution. The "Innovation Cluster for Pedagogical Education" is a mimetic method, which implies the introduction of the cluster model, which is effective in the production sectors of the economy, in the educational process. In fact, the production chains have a number of raw materials, products and demand, and this sequence is also in the form of human capital as a pedagogical education system. This indicates that the introduction of an effective cluster model in the education system is theoretically justified. In general, due to the high social importance of pedagogical education in the sustainable development of society, modern requirements, problems in the system and the discrepancy between science and education roles in the resolution of these issues require the necessity of transferring continuing pedagogical education to the cluster development model. The Innovation Cluster for Pedagogical Education is an integral part of all types of education, research institutes and centers, operational bases, scientific and scientific-methodological structures in the continuing education system, and their shared work is to elevate pedagogical education to a qualitatively new level. Hence, the cluster's main goal is to incorporate its educational and scientific innovative potential into a modern education expert

with not only high civic and professional competence but also the ability to compete, innovate, design and implement new curricula and technologies. The cluster model of the development of pedagogical education operates in the general direction of education, the creation of educational literature, raising the scientific potential of pedagogical cadres, and the continuity of education and upbringing. This shows that the problem has a general methodological character. At the same time, these generalizations are privatized in the areas such as education management and coordination, education types and trends, continuity and integration, teaching methods and tools. Subjects of the "Innovation Cluster for Pedagogical Education" model include the following:- preschool, general secondary, secondary special, higher and secondary educational establishments, which have pedagogical experience, educational, experimental, experimental base, carrying out educational, scientific, research, innovation and designing;- institutions for the adult education system, as well as retraining and advanced training of pedagogical staff of preschool, general secondary, secondary special and vocational education of children and adolescents in accordance with the changes at different levels of education; Scientific and scientific-methodological structures, centers, research institutes, engaged in scientific research activity and defining it;- pedagogical communities, initiative societies, public associations, state and non-governmental organizations;- Higher education institutions and scientific centers. The cluster model combines each of the individual entities into a common goal, and at the same time, each subject operates in a particular interest based on common purpose. The elements of the cluster model support and control each other, each of which creates a spiritual and intellectual space of a particular cluster, extends its social impact and importance. The Innovation Cluster for Pedagogical Education is based on principles such as natural affiliation, continuity, consistency, inheritance, contemporaneity, orientation, shared objectives, propriety of interests, and mutual control. We would like to highlight some of these principles:- Aim of shared goals - this principle implies the special purpose of education types and their general purpose. Within the framework of the educational cluster model, a single set of interrelated learning forms. Because the issue of cadres is the result of the full implementation of the goals set by a few subjects related to each other. It is a combination of the state education standards, quality education, the education of young people spiritually competent, physically strong, loyal to national traditions and values, and the formation of modern and non-formal thinking skills in them. - Privilege Benefit - This is a process that is naturally occurring in the production sectors of the economy. The proposed cluster model is only available when the benefits are privatized. Simply put, when the cluster subjects benefit, these actions are justified and lasting. The educational cluster model should take into account the interests of each subject. The private interests of all subjects ultimately serve for common interest.- Mutual Control - This principle means that the activities of the educational entities, which are integrated within the cluster model, are interdependent. An error or a defect in one subject affects the effectiveness of the second entity. Thus, the cluster constitutes a mutual system of learning subjects that are interconnected in a particular region or region. The main goal of the pedagogical cluster is to:- Ensuring effective pedagogy and promoting the best pupils in the pedagogical profession;- Carrying out the professional training of pedagogues on the basis of practical and operational interaction with the interested subjects;- Creating a

training environment for practitioners on the basis of internationally based practices;- Reducing the retirement age of young professionals;- Creation of a new generation of educational, methodological, scientific literature, tools and didactic materials in pedagogical education;- To increase the scientific, scientific and pedagogical potential of pedagogical education;- Integration of intellectual resources around topical issues of pedagogical education development;- search and education of different forms and types of education, science and pedagogical practice;- Improve mechanisms for education and upbringing;- Provide quick reintegration of teachers with preschool, secondary and higher education and other training;- scientific substantiation of the necessity of affiliation, linkage and cooperation between the pedagogical syllabus. Based on these goals the innovation cluster of pedagogical education performs the following functions:- Training of pedagogical staff with modern knowledge and skills for educational institutions in the region;- Effective use of innovative pedagogical technologies to improve the quality of education;- Progressive scientific activity in the field of pedagogy;- ensuring the continuity and continuity of the content and meaning of the means of education (textbooks) and auxiliary (dictionaries, guides, electronic resources, etc.);- Establishment of short term training courses in cooperation with the regional Bank for the purpose of replenishment of the level of knowledge of the teachers of educational institutions of the region;- organizing scientifically-practical seminars in cooperation with regional SEU for the elimination of problems related to teaching subjects in secondary schools;- Strengthening scientific collaboration with research institutes, research centers and other higher education institutions to enhance the scientific potential of the faculty;- involvement of teachers with the ability to carry out scientific research in general education schools in scientific research;- Implementation of internships at leading foreign HEIs to master the best foreign experience in the field of pedagogy. In general, the "Innovation Cluster of Pedagogical Education" implies achieving effectiveness through the introduction of economic models in the field of pedagogy. In this connection, the linkage and interdependence of the subjects of education, and the integration of education types will be ensured. The description of its implementation mechanisms, trends, principles, goals and objectives is one of the serious problems facing professionals. While introducing innovative innovative approaches to all sectors, present views, concepts and relationships are re-examined with the mirror of reflection and effectiveness, while presenting the cluster model is evidence that the basics are adequate when considering the issue from the point of view of relevance and modernity.

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